

Challenges that face women in senior positions at Higher Education Institutions: Experiences at the Bulawayo Polytechnic.

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Abstract.

In the past couple decades, the issue of women assuming top management and senior positions in male dominated workspaces and trades has become a topical subject. Despite their qualifications for such positions, most women have preferred to be led by a male professional instead. As such, some institutions have gone out of their comfort zones to set right what has been deemed as a prevailing gender imbalance issue, particularly in higher education institutions (HEIs). Others have even insistently taken it to the next level by deliberately encouraging them to seek those positions, thereby emboldening qualified women professionals. This article discussed this plight from a perspective of HEIs. While the inquiry established, with the use of Bulawayo Polytechnic as a case, why most women do not pursue such senior positions, it also outlined the challenges that face those who do. Part of the findings revealed social support structures was one of the mechanisms women need, to develop an attitude of interest for such appointments, and manage pressures within HEIs. The research made use of the document analysis approach to validate its claim and argument, after which, qualitative methods were employed to collect and analyse empirical evidence. Recommendations for coping strategies were also discussed.

Keywords: challenges, women, senior positions, higher education.

1. Introduction

This article assesses the challenges facing women in leadership positions at Bulawayo Polytechnic in the Bulawayo Metropolitan Province, Zimbabwe. Bulawayo Polytechnic is a technical Tertiary institution whose mandate is to develop skilled manpower in fields of Commerce, Arts and

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Engineering subjects. It has over 3000 students in both parallel and conventional programmes, a staff compliment of 315 lecturing and non-lecturing. Of the 315 then, 230 were males and 85 females (Human Resources data base, Bulawayo Polytechnic). This institution of higher learning is in the vicinity of Lupane State University, Zimbabwe Open University, United College of Education, National University of Science and Technology and the Hillside Teacher's College. Bulawayo Polytechnic is located approximately a kilometre from the central business district of Bulawayo, the second largest city of Zimbabwe.

With Bulawayo Polytechnic as the case, the study noted that the role of women has changed significantly from being passive players relegated to the domestic sphere to pronounced professionals holding leadership or management positions. Latterly, this has generally taken place in the African context as well, where women who were typically stay at home beings, have embraced career and leadership opportunities (Mathur-Helm, 2005; Adom, 2015). Historically, they could have qualifications as good as male colleagues or even better, but still fail to be recognised in terms of the skills they possessed, simply because they are women (Nikolaou, 2017). Even if women were to work, they would do general work for example, cleaning and tea services for dominantly male officers who in turn do the formal work. This has mainly been due to cultural cleavages of patriarchy that existed over time, which in the worst case of Africa, perpetuated gender imbalances (Maphosa, Tshuma and Maviza, 2015).

Since the year 2003, out of the ten state universities in Zimbabwe, only one had a woman Vice Chancellor (VC), until 2018 when an Agricultural Scientist Professor became the second woman to head a state university. However, contrary to these developments, several international and regional declarations and/or conventions had been crafted, to aid the participation of women in economic and socio-political processes, part of which would make it possible for them to head in HEIs. The Beijing conference of 2009 is one of the major milestones that brought about change in how societies view and regard women in such spheres. It has since become the podium upon which many other statutory instruments have upheld equity and equality within and between genders. Some of those statutes include the Convention on the Elimination of all forms of discrimination against Women (CEDAW), Africa Women's Rights Observatory (AWRO) and the SADC Gender Protocol, among others.

1.1. The challenge in brief

Women leaders in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) are fewer than men despite the quota system introduced by the government of Zimbabwe in 2011 (Maphosa, Tshuma and Maviza, 2015). This phenomenon on its own is not a challenge if the design is by choice, but upon general question and answer with women in senior positions at HEIs, it was established that there could be a cause-and-effect relationship to explain the nature of this establishment. It is not in black and white why women have not taken advantage of the quota system to apply for managerial posts in HEIs despite the encouragement they have been getting the past decade (Laff, 2007). It remains unclear and an area to be investigated what women administrators go through as leaders. This development could as well explain why women are discouraged from aspiring to take up such positions of leadership (Ezzedeen, Budworth and Baker, 2015).

Given the foregoing, the main purpose of this research was to inquire on the challenges facing women in leadership positions at Bulawayo Polytechnic, Zimbabwe. The study further sought to establish barriers women face rising to leadership positions. Some of the reasons that motivated the study were to eventually interpret the challenges women face in executing their duties upon assuming

leadership positions in HEIs. Finally, in the form of a discussion and recommendations, the inquiry explored the coping strategies that could be employed by women leaders to overcome the challenges.

2. Related literature

There is a regional bid to ensure that all the citizens of Africa be actively involved in decision making in all aspects, where no child, woman or man shall be left behind or excluded, on the basis of gender, political affiliation, religion, ethnicity, locality, age or other factors (African Union, 2015). This movement also attempts to ensure that African women shall be empowered entirely in all spheres, with equal rights. Zimbabwe's ZIMASSET, the country's development blue print has provisions for emancipating women under the Social service and Poverty Eradication cluster (Mapuva and Makaye, 2017). In that regard, this paper assessed the extent of women's participation or exclusion in the leadership positions using the Bulawayo Polytechnic in Zimbabwe's second Metropolitan Province as a case.

As briefly stated above, Zimbabwe has its own domestic instruments in the form of the constitution and the National Gender Policy informed by global and regional conventions on gender equality. All these instruments aim to bring the perceptions, experiences, knowledge, and interests of women as well as men to policy making, planning and decision making. Moreover, in the era of the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), MDG goal number three (3) of 2000, aims to promote gender equality and women empowerment (Simwaka *et al.*, 2005). This MDG has since evolved to be Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) number five (5) which focuses on gender equality and empowering women and girls by 2030 (Fukuda-Parr, 2016).

Feminist theories have provided theoretical background for many studies about women's development and experience. As such, the feminist theory provides a method for engaging an emancipation discourse (O'Neil, Hopkins and Bilimoria, 2015). It assists investigate the distributions of power that marginalise some and reinforce the privilege of others (Gurian, 2008). Additionally, feminist theory helps understand how intersecting aspects of individuals' identities, including gender, history, class, race, and ethnicity, shape how reality is represented. Reality viewed through the lens of social constructivism is redefined as individual perceptions of experiences filtered through the lens of multiple intersecting identities (Singleton Jr *et al.*, 1988).

The theoretical frameworks that incorporate the complexities of identity development and the intersections of race, class, and gender provided the crucial framework for this study. With regards to inquiry's context, development refers to the person's evolving conception of the environment within which they live, and their relation to it, as well as the person's growing capacity to discover, sustain, or alter its properties (Walonick, 2005). Bronfenbrenner's ecological theory (Tudge *et al.*, 2009; Christensen, 2016) of human development provided a theoretical framework through which the inquiry better understood participants' experiences of the higher education environment and the interaction of the various contexts within which women must negotiate senior positions. Although Bronfenbrenner's theory is not particularly contemporary (1979), it emphasises on perceptions, thoughts, and knowledge, hence pose as an effective framework to conducting quantitative, qualitative and mixed methods research (Onwuegbuzie, Collins and Frels, 2013). It also explains how these perceptions, thoughts, and knowledge change depending on exposure to and interaction with the environment, a perspective well-aligned with constructivist paradigms (Snaebjornsson and Edvardsson, 2013).

The metaphor of the “glass ceiling” has been used to describe invisible but very real barriers that prevent women from moving up the corporate ladder beyond a certain point (Ezzedeen, Budworth and Baker, 2015; Gandhi and Sen, 2021). While explaining the glass ceiling phenomenon, the argument was that something distressing occurs to women as they advance stages up the corporate hierarchy, that they disappear (Ezzedeen, Budworth and Baker, 2015). The discussion further reiterates that women have yet to rise to leadership levels at the same rate and pace as men. Women enter the workforce in large numbers (Gandhi and Sen, 2021), but over time steadily disappear from the higher positions of organisations (Maheshwari and Nayak, 2020). The question is why and where do they vaporise to?

Despite women advancement in education and management training, their overall employment situation in HEI positions of seniority has not evolved significantly (Crimmins, 2020, p. 16). On one hand, it is argued that the glass ceiling is more of a societal construct than an individual barrier (Jalalzai, 2013). On the other, scholars argue that corporate culture or organisational barriers are to blame (Ingley and Wu, 2007). Organisational barriers refer to the organisational-level factors that affect the differential hiring and promotion of men and women. While these barriers vary significantly from organisation to organisation, they can create a huge blockade preventing women from advancement to top management (Chamari, Anjala and Weerasighe, 2017).

3. Methodologies

The research design utilised an interpretive philosophy approach (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019), which was explanatory in nature, given that the analysis was mainly based on interview data gathered from the respondents. A purposive stratified sampling (Robinson, 2014), where the subjects were first picked based on the researchers’ knowledge of the management phenomenon under discussion, then also selected based on stratified categories that are relevant to the study. A purposive sample was also necessitated by the case study approach that the research employed to unpack the women in senior positions challenge at the institution as discussed by other scholars in similar spheres (Maheshwari and Nayak, 2020; Gandhi and Sen, 2021; Jaoul-Grammare, 2022). As such, thirty-eight (38) employees were drawn from all the Bulawayo Polytechnic management departments, as these were representative of all senior positions in the institution. The population was divided into strata mainly based on the management positions available, however such attributes as pay grade of the employees, gender, different management levels of employment also emerged during the interviews. Dividing population into a series of relevant strata ensured that the sample was representative of the senior positions in concern.

Table 1: Target Key Informant sample

Description/Population Identity	Size
Principal	1
Vice Principal	1
Heads of departments	3
Heads of divisions	6
Lecturers in charge	27
Target Population Size	38

Source: Primary Data.

Research data were collected through primary and secondary approaches and relevant authorities at the Bulawayo Polytechnic were notified. A qualitative multimethod approach was

employed where a hybrid closed-ended and open-ended questionnaire was used to collect demographic and thematic data respectively. Interested stakeholders were engaged for permissions and ethical clearances. Based on the research questions and in the light of the review of related literature, the questionnaire was designed such that the set choice of questions could easily be coded for ease of thematic analysis and to obtain relevant demographic data. This enabled identification and description of the variability in different phenomena. As such, it was divided into three main sections namely the Management, Heads of divisions/departments and Lecturers in charge. Closed ended questions were designed for coded numerical analysis while open ended questions were designed for coded thematic/sentimental analysis (Pong-Inwong and Songpan, 2019).

Each respondent was asked to answer identical questions as indicated on the questionnaire and all 38 participants were interviewed successfully. The approach to the design of the questionnaire followed these two foundations identified by Walonick (2005); preliminary framework built on the review of theory from academic literature prior to design of questionnaires; and pilot use of questionnaire to allow for restructuring of questions where necessary. Using Bronfenbrenner's ecological theory of human development as a theoretical framework for the inquiry, the study analysed how women have transitionally evolved in the workplace based on their current interactions and adaptations to the new environments around them. The support and encouragement they have from global and national organisations as mentioned in the literature, assist in righting the wrongs that used to predominantly eclipse their aspirations. Interviews based on open ended questions assisted to capture the views that otherwise would not have been captured through closed ended questions for such an inquiry. The study took note of expressions like body language, facial expressions and audible tone as participants answered some of the sensitive questions of the survey. This was done through face to face and telephonic communication with the participants. The semi-structured interviews were particularly useful to comprehend the story behind a participant's experiences and hence assisted the interviewees to express their opinions, concerns, and feelings.

All coded data were analysed in the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). However, some themes were developed from the sentiments of respondents. These were the major data gathered from which the analysis and discussion were based. Closed-ended questions at the beginning of the interview, especially in the case of demographic data were used to help establish some relationships between concepts, concerns and the different backgrounds of participants in their latter responses to the open-ended questions. For instance, knowing gender differences was the only way that could have helped inform and explicate the different levels of sentiments and what the gender challenges really meant for the different respondents. All other interpretations based on the findings of open-ended question interviews were presented as narrative text. All qualitative data from archival evidence were analysed qualitatively and that included coming up with issues or themes of analysis.

4. Challenges that face women in senior positions: Findings and Case analysis

One of the most common and well-known barriers to career advancement is that of the selection process used by most companies. The generality of this fact is that, in most organisations, selection is not a publicised exercise, hence the assumed point five to point five (0.5:0.5) probability chance of equity is not visible to those outside the system. As indicated previously, the pool of women that are qualified for promotion to executive positions is quite small and therefore the odds for promotion are probably also slim. One survey on the Fortune 500 firms in the USA stated that lack of

general management skills and line experience was a major factor in their decisions not to promote women to executive positions. As a result, women held 11.9% of Fortune 500 senior positions up from 8.2% in 1995 (Nelson and Burke, 2000). Although an improvement, the same survey also revealed that a mere 12% of women were in senior positions in Canadian corporates. A related study established that some firms have a large pool of qualified women but simply do not consider them for senior positions (Burke *et al.*, 2000). A correlated rationale suggests that existing top management positions are held by men who tend to promote other men similar to themselves (Nikolaou, 2017).

Another organisational barrier is the relationships many women have with their mentors, bosses, and women co-workers. Most employees tend to bond through similar interests. Since there tends to be few women executives; several other aspirational women are unable to find a suitable (woman) mentor. Women are inhibited in the workplace because of their limited access to capable mentors of similar interests (Reciniello, 2011). Many people prefer to have mentors of the same gender because they tend to understand the challenges most faced. Men do not face the same barriers, nor have the same cumbersome family issues as compared to women, and many a times men simply do not desire to mentor a woman. This is based on part of the sentimental analyses established from the interview responses of the male sample population.

The study also revealed that needs of women tend to differ from the needs of men when it comes to mentorship. Most women need more encouragement; a role model to emulate; and more simplified tasks to complete as part of learning and adjustment; a structure they claim is nearly non-existent in the current situation. Male mentors tend to be resistant to mentor a woman because they perceive women as more emotive, not as skilled at problem-solving, and also because of the risk of workplace sexual harassment issues (Elmuti, Jia and Davis, 2009). This is a notion that needs further scrutiny; if there really are grounds to support these claims and issues at the HEI workplace. It is not clearly articulated how emotions affect women's duties, which is otherwise another discussion on its own.

Globalization and spatial growth of HEIs also present new obstacles for women. Senior level managers and top executives now have even more responsibility and higher expectations than yesteryear. Due to the competition pressure, relocation, and expansion of many HEIs, top executives have had to move to new towns, cities, and in some cases countries. This presents a sizable impediment for many women with families and a spouse or significant other (Lukaka, 2013; Ruiz, 2018). While the largest problem has been raising a family from miles apart, women were also shown to be affected by adaptation to new cultures and social norms. A large number of women have been unable to handle the culture shock and expectations, hence fail in their new environments (Burke *et al.*, 2000; Lukaka, 2013). Similarly, in other patriarchal cultures, women may also experience social conflict in rising to leadership posts. The patriarchal nature of leadership positions in other countries, for example in southern Africa, lessen women's aspirations to hold leadership positions (Archard, 2013).

A sizable number of senior executive and top management at Bulawayo Polytechnic claim that women simply do not have an aspiration to excel beyond their current positions. However, another separate but minor survey (used as secondary data) in the same institute indicated that 55% of women employed in positions other than management desire to be in the topmost levels of the organisation. This was in most cases ironically influenced by seeing other women hold those senior level positions. In such a case, as discussed earlier in this article, one of the greatest deterrents is that women lack mentors with similar interests, struggles, passions, and drive. It can however be argued as well, that this is more of personal perceptions than reality. Many women lose their drive to excel due to the many obstacles met along the path of becoming a manager. These obstacles include general lack of

mentorship, discrimination, stereotyping, prejudice, family demands, and lack of opportunities (Zhang, 2009).

Women's prioritisation of family roles at the expense of their career advancement is not new. For example, culturally feminine behaviour is nurturing and caring for others, placing importance on relationships and the quality of life (Elmuti, Jia and Davis, 2009). Women executives at the Bulawayo Polytechnic exhibited the same characteristics. They would adjourn a work-related meeting to take care of a pressing family matter. On the other hand, men would finish the business of the day before engaging in family matters. Therefore, women are perceived as caring, nurturing and collaborative, while men are rendered much more analytical, decisive, data-rational, and competitive. The management then argues that the same qualities of caring, nurturing and collaboration should otherwise drive the women to desire senior positions. In that light of these qualities, this reiterates that women really do not have the same desire and drive as they should.

Nonetheless, women have distinct leadership traits and skills in leading educational institutions, even though they face certain difficulties and challenges that hamper their leadership effectiveness (Rodriguez, 2016). They can balance between their work as a HEI leader and the family role despite all the various pressures, given the fact that for most of the women interviewed, they had to fulfil both duties. This does not mean that men had no family roles to fulfil but that for women, doing both was a new and challenging height. The issue of prioritisation was not as much a problem for men as it was for women. The study also showed that there is a clear bias towards men than women in the assumption of administrative leadership positions, an indication of marginalisation against women's aspirations to take up leadership roles.

Sexual harassment is one of the major challenges that faces both women aspiring to assume senior positions and those already there. Sexual harassment refers to persistent and unwanted sexual advances, typically in the workplace, where the consequences of refusing are potentially very disadvantaging to the victim. It includes the actions of a person or group (usually of the opposite sex) repeatedly sending threatening, unwelcoming, or unsettling letters, calling on phone, or repeatedly sending unwanted gifts to the victim (Belle, 2017). Compared to men, proportionally more decisions made by women were overruled by higher status male aggressors, indicating the use of an indirect form of harassment (De Pater et al., 2009). Again, women were more likely to report if assigned extra-heavy workloads; if they completed tasks outside of their job descriptions; and if threatened by aggressors who attempted to make their lives at work difficult. Thus, women were frequently susceptible to indirect forms of harassment.

5. Discussion

From the findings of the study, both women and men had a similar perception of what a senior position is and what it means for one to be in that position. However, the same expressed different views on the choice of leadership styles, a breakaway point that led to the predicament of fewer women in senior HEI positions. There seemed to be three major elements that women focus on in their career paths before they could become successful HEI senior managers, and these came coupled with challenges specific to them. If these were not properly taken care of the study revealed that women would not achieve the goal of senior positions in HEIs.

The first and the most prevalent element they needed to know and understand better in order not to fail in their endeavour, especially with regards to the African perspective, was culture. They

pointed out that culture has been the biggest element they needed to observe which at some point divided their lives into two separates. An interesting intersection about culture in this case is that it referred to both organisational and societal culture. Women had to be a senior manager on one hand and on the other adhere to the expectations of a woman in the cultural societal community. On the values of societal culture, emanated inter-alia, issues of patriarchy; prioritisation imbalances of men over women; inevitable upholding respect and honour for men; and on the values of organisation similar issues still prevailed where respect and honour for men personnel by women employees were naturally embedded in the organisational culture; and more distressing, activities of sexual harassment. Women indicated that because of the construct of most African cultures and traditions, women have been sexually objectified by men in the workplace and expected to take such acts as compliments in the name of “cultural” reverence.

The second element women needed to think largely about before they could start a career for themselves as senior managers at HEIs was the family unit. This element, which is closely linked to culture, poses serious challenges to senior management women if not planned for in the beginning of the career. Men have indicated that in the case of a new-born baby in the family, they are expected to continue coming to work as usual while women are given a special treatment called the maternity leave. This has made women to seem incompetent when they take long leave away from work to nurture babies. Again, potential young women have thus shied away from senior positions because of having to choose between work and family. This could also be the reason why most sitting women executives (in an African context) are either elderly women or younger without a “conventional” family, a claim that needs further investigation in future studies. Women managers in the patriarchal African context, must comprehended the issues in planning for a family to avoid such instances that male counterparts are always on the lookout for, discrediting them as dependable leaders at those HEIs.

The third and last major element the study gathered from analysis was that the area of ethics, discipline and conduct is sensitive especially with regards to senior positions hence there is high level prejudice. According to the women, one main form of prejudice they needed to take care of was getting over the issues of chauvinism and stereotyping, as they pointed that it would be long before these come to an end at HEIs. An example that came from the findings was the issue of advertisements coined with the phrase “women are encouraged to apply.” Some women expressed that this was an unethical and derogatory term that assumed women had no potential to advance themselves in their own accord. It suggested that they constantly need a nudge to uplift themselves unlike their male counterparts. However, contrary to the concerns raised, that clause also promotes bias on women candidates. This bias could, nonetheless, be explained as a corrective measure for the flaws that still characterise the promotions into senior positions at HEIs which are still dominated by men (Crimmins, 2020; Maheshwari and Nayak, 2020; Gandhi and Sen, 2021; Jaoul-Grammare, 2022).

In terms of conduct and discipline, there was a thin line separating the authority of a male executive as a disciplinarian in the society (cultural space) and in the workplace. Men’s positions in the society augmented their positions as senior executives in HEIs. On the other hand, women executives faced difficulties in holding disciplinarian positions over male subordinates because of the cultural and societal contexts. It was established that, while it was easy for a young man executive to call to order an elderly woman subordinate, it was not the same case with young women executives towards an elderly man. Women executives, because of cultural upbringing, saw a father figure in elderly men subordinates, hence were reserved in restraining them. In such cases, women leaders needed to fully understand and advocate for improved policies that emancipate them from such prejudices before their careers took off.

5.1. Recommendations for coping strategies

Men executives have over the years built societies where they discuss leadership challenges and opportunities outside the formal working hours. For women executives the journey is still quite long. The starting point, however, is no doubt to learn from male counterparts. While this does not claim one party as better than the other, it just presents a strategy that can be adopted. Apart from business management schools where everyone has a chance to enrol in, male executives have a lot of other support structures that women executives are not privy to. What makes this occurrence even more unbalanced is that some of these structures are accessible to male non-executive members. This places those men to an advantage over women opponents should they aspire to become senior executives in HEIs.

Men have sports clubs, where they discuss important business that potentially affect the future and they do this in between games. They have executive pubs where they groom and nurture young aspirants outside the formal working hours. One highly ignored contributor is the bars and pubs within the HEIs. Seldom would women be found in those facilities discussing matters pertinent to their future successes. These coping and future planning strategies cannot be the same per se, but women need to use these examples as a starting point to build their own support structures with regards. One tool that men utilise and always gives them a greater competitive advantage over women is that of social capital. Social capital as a result, is built outside formal structures and its snowballing growth is enhanced in such social spaces as those discussed above.

Social gatherings (churches, women's conferences, feminist movement gatherings, etc) that are at the reach of women, are equally supposed to work as encouragement centres for future leadership aspirants. Seldom is it the case that a religious gathering will have a business or leadership chapter for women to discuss their advancement strategies. While the adaptive coping strategies (Plessis, 2020) mention cognitive, emotional, leisure and religious coping units, they do not delve into the intricacies of implementation strategies in detail. In essence, women need to deliberately transform those gatherings not only as a way of steaming off pressures that mount on them at work, but also as a platform to build and nurture new and upcoming future women leaders.

6. Conclusions and way forward

In conclusion, several studies have revealed that there is a resounding gap and the need for more women leaders in HEIs in the future. They further reveal that there is a correlation between the success of women and that of organisations and societies. When women succeed; there tends to be desirable outcomes in their societies as well. While government has a huge role to play in policy formulation and elimination of bias to balance gender and equity, the onus largely lies with the already achieved women. They must create networks to mentor other women into becoming future senior management. The "glass ceiling" predicament is persistent, the study found out that some women would surely pass at an opportunity to pursue a senior position if the field is male dominated. Perceptions they have predominantly conceived about leadership positions at HEIs makes it difficult to consider applying. The women encouragement centres and networks if at all will be prioritised as they ought to be, can really alleviate the issue of non-attempt. As part of the recommendations, there needs to be a deliberate address of the "qualified but not skilled and experienced" phenomenon (Nelson and Burke, 2000). It is a barrier to most women. Similarly, women might need to work around the barrier of losing interest in a position if a mentor is not female like them (Reciniello, 2011). Equally

important for future consideration, a development that arose during the interviews, is the question of whether emotions affect women's duties at HEIs. Also interesting, would be an examination of the correlation between a relatively young woman and her starting a "conventional" family or attaining a senior HEI position. This was necessitated by an observation that relatively young women in senior positions had not started a family yet, while those who held senior positions and had a "conventional" family too, were more elderly in comparison. Lastly, as a way of further investigating these challenges, it would be interesting if future work can empirically examine the concept of a glass ceiling to understand how it really plays a constraining role in women qualified for managerial positions.

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